

EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL ON EQUITY FINANCING COSTS IN NIGERIAN MANUFACTURING COMPANIES

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Abstract: *This study determined the effect of intellectual capital on cost of capital of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. To accomplish this objective, this study employed longitudinal research design and a panel data set sourced from annual financial reports of a sample made up of forty-two (42) manufacturing companies listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group Limited (NGX) over an 11-year period beginning from year 2012 to year 2022. The study modelled cost of equity as the function of human capital efficiency, structural capital efficiency, capital employed efficiency and relational capital efficiency. A multilevel mixed-effects linear regression analysis technique was employed. Broadly, the results reveal mixed evidence suggesting that the effect of intellectual capital management on cost of equity is dependent on the unique characteristics of the proxy employed. The outcome indicates that human capital efficiency has an insignificant effect on cost of equity capital. Structural capital showed an insignificant effect on both cost of equity capital. Capital employed revealed a significant negative effect on cost of equity capital while relational capital has no significant effect on cost of equity capital. Based on these empirical outcomes, the study recommended amongst others, that policy makers such as the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade, and Investment (FMITI) should promote and support initiatives that encourage manufacturing firms to invest in workforce development, training, and skill enhancement to equip the workforce with skills that align with industry demands.*

Ibehto Anthony A. and Given I. Nwodimkpa

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge and expertise are essential resources that can be utilised to solve problems, add value, and provide strategic advantages. In today's fast-paced economy with the rapid expansion of knowledge and technological advancements, organisational growth has evolved to adapt to this shifting landscape. In today's competitive global economy, intellectual capital has emerged as a crucial element for organisations to thrive and add value in their operating environment. Within a knowledge-driven economy, intellectual capital (IC) plays a crucial role as a valuable resource for enhancing firms' value, fostering growth, and fueling innovation (Lev, 2004; Chen, Chen, & Hwang, 2005; Wang, Wang, & Liang, 2014; Dženopoljac, Yaacoub, & Elkanj, 2017). As highlighted in the research by Cao and Zhang (2011), the current era is characterised by a knowledge-based economy. Companies are increasingly focusing on leveraging intellectual resources over physical assets to thrive in the ever-evolving business landscape. Therefore, countries are transitioning from focusing on production and labour to emphasising knowledge and knowledge workers. Intangible assets, particularly knowledge, are becoming increasingly important for companies looking to survive and gain a competitive edge in strategic competition (Latif, Malik & Aslam, 2012). According to Bontis (2001), intellectual

capital is now the key factor for ensuring the long-term success of companies.

Investments in intellectual capital, also known as intangible assets, complement tangible investments and lead to future benefits. They significantly contribute to value creation through employee knowledge, organisational processes, and innovation. According to Gross-Gołacka, Kusterka-Jefmanska, and Jefmanski (2020), intellectual capital is crucial for sustainable development. Within the knowledge economy, the value of intangible resources like intellectual capital is crucial for firms to gain economic benefits and establish a competitive edge alongside tangible asset. (Jardon 2015; Xu & Wang 2018; Oppong, Pattanayak, & Irfan 2019; Cisneros, Perlins, & Garcia, 2020; Xu & Liu 2021). Highlighting the significance of intellectual assets for companies in managing innovation and exploitative activities is essential in the era of the fourth industrial revolution (Mahmood & Mubarik, 2020). Companies that continue to invest in new skills and technology are poised to succeed, as intellectual capital emerges as a crucial asset for longterm viability. The study conducted by Aljuboori, Singh, Haddad, Al-Ramahi, & Ali in 2022. Roos, Roos, Dragonetti, and Edvinsson, (1997) as in Ross, Westerfield, and Jaffe (2010) described intellectual capital as the total of intangible assets like human capital, structural capital, and relational capital, with human capital

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embodying the organization's knowledge. Structural capital encompasses all non-human knowledge reservoirs such as databases, organisational charts, and process implementation instructions, among other valuable assets for an organisation beyond their material worth. Senyucel, (2009) referenced Stewart (1997) to highlight that the core focus of relational capital involves understanding marketing channels and customer relationships. Regarding the cost of capital, Salvi, Vitolla, Raimo, Rubino, and Petruzzella (2020) and Tarigan, Listijabudhi, Hatane, & Widjaja (2019) emphasise that the cost of capital is a crucial factor in assessing investment choices. Ensuring that a company's financial statements including its profitability are transparent can help reduce uncertainty surrounding shareholders' equity and lower the cost of capital. According to Bianchi Martini, Corvino, Doni, and Rigolini (2016), when a company's financial statements lack clarity and completeness, stakeholders may face increased uncertainty, potentially resulting in higher return demands. Managers are essential in reducing the company's cost of capital to enhance the company's value and increase shareholder wealth as they act on behalf of the shareholders. It is highlighted by Myers and Majluf (1984) as well as Reilly and Brown (2011) that the cost of capital has consistently been a focal point for financial experts, leading to discrepancies between accounting profit and

economic profit. Considering the cost of capital as a valuable opportunity for investors to interact with the company is essential from two angles: Firstly, all securities valuation models are dependent on the cost of capital, and secondly, making decisions on investment priorities and capital structures without considering the cost of capital would not be practical (Salimi & Ahmed, 2007).

Many studies have provided evidence suggesting a possible adverse connection between the management of intellectual assets and capital costs. According to Goebel (2015), more extensive reporting on intellectual capital may lead to a reduction in the cost of capital, consistent with the findings of Barus and Siregar (2015) and Mangena, Li, and Tauringana (2014) emphasising the influence of intellectual capital on reducing the cost of capital. Highlighting the importance of categorising information disclosure into intellectual capital and financial specifics for a better understanding of capital expenses as per Bontis, Keow, and Richardson (2001), there exists an adverse relationship between managing intellectual assets and the cost of capital, particularly in the context of forward-looking intellectual capital data. In a study conducted by García-Sánchez and Noguera-Gámez (2017), they discovered an effect of managing intellectual capital on capital cost. On the other hand, Boujelbene and Affes (2013) propose that only human and structural

capital assets play a role in lowering the cost of capital. According to a study conducted by Francis, Nanda, and Olsson (2008), it was proposed that three specific measures of intellectual capital are essential in lowering the cost of capital for companies: the number of employees, average wage per employee, and market share. Additional characteristics were discovered to have little or no effect on the cost of capital.

On the other hand, Botosan and Plumlee (2002) discovered a positive nexus partly linked to the concept that enhanced disclosure attracts investors, leading to heightened volatility and consequently increases capital expenses. These differing viewpoints have raised concerns and questions, prompting a study on how managing intellectual assets affects the capital costs of manufacturing companies listed in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW Intellectual Capital

The concept of intellectual capital was initially introduced by Galbraith (1969) as in Baron (2011); opined that IC is the “process of value creation.” Thereafter, Baron (2011) further demonstrated that Intellectual Capital (IC) involves investment in suppliers, customers, employers and technology. El-Bannany (2008) citing the work of Bell (1997) in his study explains Intellectual Capital (IC) in terms of an organisation’s competitive advantage by having access to a resource, which includes the forms,

strategies and unique methods utilized to create the advantage. Intellectual Capital (IC) is further defined as knowledge synthesis, information, skills, experience and learning capacity (Goebel (2015). Adler and Kwon (2002) claimed IC is concealed between the market and the book value of a firm.

Different investigators have categorized IC differently. For example, Brooking and Motta (1996) in Alkhateeb, Yao, and Kie (2018) suggest that intellectual capital consists of human capital, structural capital, and knowledge property rights capital. Edvinsson and Malone (1997) in Firer and Williams (2003) categorised intellectual capital into human capital and structural capital. Human resources determine the skills, mindset, and intelligence of employees, while structural assets encompass the organization's framework, equipment, and facilities. Sveiby (1997) categorised intellectual capital into human capital, structural capital, and customer capital.

Human Capital Efficiency (HCE)

The broad concept of human capital efficiency confines a lot of components yet describes the workforce quality. Measurement of human capital as a source of innovation and improvement in an organization is an element that is challenging with many attempts to define it. According to Stockley (2003), human capital acknowledges people working in an organisation and sees them as a key and indispensable asset

that come up with the development and growth in a similar way to physical assets like machines and money. According to Baron (2011), human resources is a component of knowledge, skills ability to develop and be creative by employees of a company. Shih, Chen, & Morrison, (2010) opposed the affirmation that human capital can be traded and is owned by organisations, instead the employee's knowledge and professional skills belong to the employee.

Structural Capital Efficiency (SCE)

Structural capital pertains to the internal framework of the organisation, including processes and procedures. It encompasses patents, organisational processes, strategic and administrative technologies (Edvinsson & Malone, 1997). Fundamentally, structural capital refers to the internal organization that supports human capital to create value for organization and financial health (Sveiby, 1997). In the views of Stewart, (1997); Bontis, (1998); structural capital comprises information systems, databases, copyrights, patents, processes and relationship with others to support the human resources. Similar to the position of Sveiby, (1997) structural capital as identified by Zeglal and Zigan, (2014) refers to the conditions and structures that provide an enabling environment for the human capital to function effectively. Stewart (1997) suggested that structural capital could be owned in common while others could be of great strategic value. Structural capital that

cannot be replicated (as a criterion under the resource-based theory) in other companies become a great source of competitive advantage; therefore, the management process of complementing human capital with structural capital is important which becomes the internal processes and achievements that a firm may capitalise on.

Capital Employed Efficiency

Capital Employed (CE) is the amount of capital investment a firm use to steer and give indications on the money a company invests. This can be referred to as the capital a company utilises to bring about profits (Daniel, 2020). The CE can mean the asset value of all assets a company uses to generate income (Sherry, 2016). Capital Employed efficiency is defined as the ratio of incurred dollar expenditure of a company and the spent dollar to produce a service (Hayes, 2020). This metric provides the efficiency of capital used to ensure the production of a service or product and affords the company an enhanced opportunity to gain profit (Adams, 2020). When the amount of employed capital is high and not collected from the equity shareholders, the risk level is higher than expected and informs the company of aggressive business expansion and growth in plans. When the plans are successful, it is considered to provide a higher return on investment to the investors (Adam, 2020).

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Relational Capital Efficiency

Relational Capital Efficiency (RCE) is a concept that focuses on the management and utilization of relational capital, which refers to the intangible assets that arise from a firm's relationships and interactions with its stakeholders, including customers, suppliers, employees, and partners. RCE emphasizes the effectiveness and efficiency with which a firm leverages its relational capital to achieve its strategic objectives and enhance its overall performance. The literature on RCE highlights its significance in today's highly interconnected and relationship-driven business environment. Various studies emphasize the importance of relational capital in creating value and achieving sustainable competitive advantage. Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) define relational capital as the "combination of shared norms and values, trust, mutual understanding, and shared goals within relationships." These relationships contribute to knowledge sharing, innovation, and enhanced firm performance.

Research shows a positive relationship between RCE and firm performance. For instance, Hitt, Ireland, and Lee (2000) finds that firms that effectively manage their relational capital have higher financial performance, market value, and customer satisfaction. Similarly, Lin and Lee (2012) reveal that RCE positively influences firm innovation and market performance. Further, trust is a crucial component of relational capital.

High-quality relationships characterized by trust, mutual understanding, and cooperation lead to better outcomes. Morgan and Hunt (1994) emphasize the importance of trust in building and maintaining long-term relationships, which in turn enhances firm performance.

Concept of Cost of Capital

The concept of "cost of capital" refers to the required rate of return that a company or investor must earn on its investments to maintain the value of its existing assets and attract additional investments. It is a crucial concept in finance and capital budgeting, as it helps businesses and investors make decisions about allocating resources to various projects and investments. In simpler terms, the cost of capital is the price a company pays for using funds from different sources to finance its operations or expansion. These sources of funds typically include equity (stockholders' investment) and debt (borrowed funds). Practically, the resources for the firm come from two sources: the owners of equity and the owners of financial debt. The cost the firm pays for the resources that it must obtain to make the investments is not so evident. Here it is necessary to consider not only what is paid in terms of interest on a financial debt, but also what the shareholders *expect* to earn. In any case, firms pay for the use of funds from third

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parties and that price is the cost of capital (Velez-Pareja & Tham, 2011).

Cost of Equity Capital

Cost of equity (COE) as an important concept in financial management helps to determine whether a firm's investment activity is feasible or not. It is the return that a company must realize in exchange for a given investment or project. Further, it represents the return that shareholders expect on their investment in the company. Investors expect a return that reflects the risk associated with investing in the company's stock. Various factors impact the cost of equity, including the company's risk profile, market conditions, and the potential returns from alternative investments with comparable risk levels. It's crucial to consider the cost of equity when making decisions about securing additional funding for a new project. Understanding the timing and amount of capital expenditures required to support the firm's investments is a key responsibility of the financial manager (Arief, 2009).

Utami (2005), note that the cost of equity represents the return rate on the stock that investors demand, with the minimum return rate expected by investors looking to invest in the company. Investors' risk tolerance when investing in a company is reflected in the compensation they receive as the cost of equity. From an investor's perspective, there is an anticipation of receiving returns either through

dividends or an appreciation in the investment's value. The cost of equity has a link with the financial risk contained in the funds invested in the firm's business (Tanjung, 2014).

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